

Paper 2

AN EVOLUTION OF AUTONOMOUS VEHICLE- A CASE STUDY OF WAYMO

Srivatsa Maddodi^{1,2} and Krishna Prasad. K.³

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

²Data Engineer Specialist, Analytics and Data Management, DXC Technology, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India

³College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India
Email: srivatsa.maddodi@gmail.com

Abstract

Waymo is one of the subsidiaries of Alphabet Inc. Initially Waymo Started as project in google for Self-driving or Autonomous vehicle from year 2009 and it was led by Sebastian Thrun. Before Google Thrun led a team at Stanford Artificial Intelligence Laboratory as a director. He was co-inventor of Google Street View. Google Street View is one of the important features in Google Maps. Waymo released its first prototype in the year 2014 and in 2015 it tested the worlds first ride of driverless car in the public roads. There were various concerns expressed by the lawmakers for the safety of Autonomous Vehicle. A limited trail of Self driving taxi services were started in the year April 2017 in Phoenix, Arizona. After its success a commercial service called Waymo One was launched in the year 2018 December 5. Waymo has partnership with many Vehicle manufacturing companies like Jaguar Land Rover, Fiat Chrysler Automobiles, Renault-Nissan etc. Unlike its rival Tesla Motors which is into autonomous Cars business Waymo produces kit which can be deployed across multiple vehicles of different vendors. Currently road tests are under way for Self-Driving trucks. Waymo became an independent subsidiary of Alphabet Inc in the year 2016. In this paper we analyze various business strategies of Waymo, including new product development. This paper analyzes how Waymo with the help of technology improve the autonomous vehicle making transportation safe and secure for everyone. Based on the SWOT analysis we have provided some suggestion that can be incorporated by Netflix as business strategy.

Keywords: Waymo, Autonomous Vehicle, Google Self-driving cars, Robo-taxi, Alphabet Inc.

1.INTRODUCTION:

Waymo is technology company that mainly focuses on self-driving of automobiles. Initially started within Google in the year 2009 at the Google secret lab facility run by the Google co-founder Sergey Brin. The team was led by Sebastian Thrun. Before Google Sebastian Thrun led a team at Stanford Artificial Intelligence Laboratory as a director. He was co-inventor of Google Street View. Google Street View is one of the important features in Google Maps. At Stanford Sebastian Thrun led a team of 15 members which created a robotic vehicle called Stanley which

participated and won in the 2005 DARPA Challenge [1]. From 2009 till 2012 Google employees started developing the technology and sensors and started testing it on highways. Then they started to focus on complex streets in the cities which includes pedestrians, obstacles like traffic jam and road work, road diversion due to repairs or traffic jam, traffic signals and more. After rigorous testing by google employees in the year 2015 Google introduced Firefly which is 100% autonomous. These had no steering wheels and pedals all the things were automated having sensors and computer steering and breaking system. Steven Mahan who is legally Blind took the worlds first public ride in autonomous car [2]. In the year 2016 Google Self Driving project became Waymo which is subsidiary of Alphabet Inc and focuses on self-driving technology, safety of passengers along with ease of use. In the year 2017 Waymo began testing on Chrysler Pacifica Hybrid making it a 100 % autonomous minivan without driver. In 2018 it started the cab services in Phoenix, Arizona. Waymo is currently focusing on assembling the kit of existing cars rather than developing new design like Firefly. Waymo has tie ups. Waymo has partnership with many Vehicle manufacturing companies like Jaguar Land Rover, Fiat Chrysler Automobiles, Renault-Nissan etc. Unlike its rival Tesla Motors which is into autonomous Cars business Waymo produces kit which can be deployed across multiple vehicles of different vendors. Currently road tests are under way for Self-Driving trucks.

2.OBJECTIVES:

Below are the objectives of study

1. To understand about the Technology used in Waymo autonomous cars.
2. To Understand how Waymo Autonomous cars work.
3. Use of SWOT analysis for recommendation of Waymo future strategies.

3.LIDAR TECHNOLOGY:

Waymo cars are based on the LIDAR Technology (Light Detection and Ranging) with the use of Laser distance is measured from source to target. Time taken laser light return from target and wavelengths are used to Three-dimensional representation of the target or high-resolution maps[3-4]. Some of the main components of lidar systems are Laser, GPS Receiver, Scanner, optics and photodetector. In Waymo Lidar is mainly used for Obstacle detection and road environment mapping. In Lidar hexagonal mirrors are used to split the laser beams. The upper beams are used to detect the obstacles like vehicle etc and the lower beams are used to detect the road features like lanes, markings dividers etc.

3.WORKING OF WAYMO CARS:

Waymo works by answering below principle questions

1. Where am I?
2. What's around me?
3. What will happen next?
4. What Should I do?

Where am I? Before the testing of autonomous car begins on any road or location Waymo team will build their own detailed maps which includes information's such as road profiles, sidewalks, markers on the lane, traffic signals, any other signals and road features.

What's around me? The sensors installed on the autonomous vehicle constantly scan for the objects around the vehicle like other vehicles, pedestrians, any obstruction due to road work, traffic signals, railroads etc. Waymo autonomous vehicles can detect distances or obstacles up to three football field in every direction.

What will happen next? The software installed in waymo autonomous vehicle predicts the movements of all the objects or vehicles based on the trajectory and speed. It differentiates the movement of pedestrians, vehicles and cyclist. The software uses the information to predict the many possible paths the other road user may take.

What should I do? Based on all the information available the waymo software determines exact speed, driving lane the vehicle must take in order to travel safely.

4.ANALYSIS:

SWOT Analysis is performed as per guidelines mentioned in Case Studies [5-11]

Strengths:

- Well Established brand name of Google.
- Safer Transportation in ideal environment.
- Less Stressful driving experience.
- Convivence and luxury.

Weakness:

- Highly dependent on Technology.
- Technology is still in testing phase and not fully operational.
- Legal requirements.
- Cars are expensive.

Opportunity:

- Huge potential market to capture.
- Can explore market of Heavy Vehicles.

Threats:

- Misuse of Technology.
- Privacy Concerns of User data.

5.SUGGESTION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the SWOT analysis below are the few recommendations

- Waymo needs to keep invested in technology making it more advanced and affordable.
- Waymo still needs to improve the driving experience making it more safe and secure by adhering to transportation laws.

- Waymo need to improve the manufacturing process more efficient making the autonomous cars affordable.
- Tie-ups with different car manufacture for implementing autonomous driving.

6.CONCLUSION:

In this paper we have discussed regarding the concepts of autonomous vehicle and technology used by Waymo in autonomous cars. We have briefly explained about Lidar Technology and the working of Waymo cars. Finally based on the SWOT analysis we have provided some recommendations to improve efficiency of Waymo.

REFERENCES

- [1] Waymo, Wikipedia, Accessed: 09-Nov-2019, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Waymo>
- [2] History of Google Car Project, Accessed: 09-Nov-2019, <https://www.businessinsider.com/google-car-project-history-2018-8#a-purpose-built-self-driving-vehicle-called-fire-fly-enters-the-picture-in-2014-5>
- [3] Lidar: driving the future of autonomous navigation. Frost & Sullivan, CA, USA, 2016.
- [4] Rasshofer, R. H., Gresser, K. (2005): Automotive radar and lidar systems for next generation driver assistance function. *Adv. Radio Sci.*, 3, 205–209.
- [5] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Industry Analysis – The First Step in Business Management Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 1-13. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810347>.
- [6] Aithal, P. S. and Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(7), 231-247. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163425>.
- [7] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An Effective Method of Developing Business Case Studies Based on Company Analysis. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 16-27. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.400579>.
- [8] Aithal, P. S., (2017). ABCD Analysis as Research Methodology in Company Case Studies. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 40-54. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.891621>.
- [9] Aithal P. S. (2017). Impact of Domestic, Foreign, and Global Environments on International Business Decisions of Multinational Firms: A Systematic Study. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 57-73. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1067103>.
- [10] Aithal, P. S., (2017). Company Analysis – The Beginning Step for Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(1), 1-18. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.573769>.
- [11] Aithal, P. S. and Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, 5(7), 231-247. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163425>.